

Depression, Disability and Student Well-being: A Conceptual Exploration

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Abstract- A corporate entity is a legally recognized organization such as a corporation, limited liability company (LLC), or partnership that exists separately from its owners or shareholders. As a distinct legal person, it possesses its own legal rights and responsibilities, enabling it to enter into contracts, own property, incur debts, sue or be sued, and pay taxes independently of its owners. One of the primary advantages of this structure is limited liability, which protects the personal assets of shareholders or members from the debts and obligations of the business.

Keywords- Stakeholders, Shareholders, Corporate, Legal Entity, Shareholders Primacy, Corporate Governance, Social, Environment, Stakeholder-oriented, Strategies, Company Board.

I. Introduction

Depression is a common mental health issue that deeply affects students in schools and colleges (Eisenberg, Hunt, & Speer, 2013). According to the American College Health Association's National College Health Assessment, around 30% of college students reported feeling so depressed at some point in the past year that it became hard to carry on with their daily activities (American College Health Association, 2018). The World Health Organization (WHO) points out that depression is one of the leading causes of disability across the world, affecting nearly 264 million people globally (World Health Organization, 2020). Among students, depression often leads to serious problems like poor academic performance, irregular attendance, and a higher chance of dropping out (Eisenberg et al., 2009).

